

IOM Framework

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1. Question: After reviewing the Institute of Medicine (IOM) website (www.iom.edu), describe the IOM report framework for healthcare quality. How can it be applied to nursing? How can it be applied to your actual work setting?

The primary purpose of the IOM Framework is to study a wide array of healthcare concerns. The website clearly states that a majority of the studies that it undertakes are initiated as a result of specific mandates that are directed by the congress. Apart from this, other studies undertaken by the IOM are directed by federal agencies or other independent organizations. The studies undertaken by the IOM consist of extensive research on the proposed areas of study and since they are funded by the government, it is less likely that studies will be scrapped or ended due to lack of sufficient funds.

Unfortunately, the projects being carried out by the IOM have been put on hold due to the recent shutdown of the government of the United States. This is mainly because of a lack of directives from the government to follow on with the projects, most of which are government directed. However, there is sufficient evidence to suggest that the studies conducted by IOM are thorough. The IOM has been among the pioneers of innovation in the field of medical research. The studies conducted by the institute have helped several agencies in making the right decisions.

The same framework can be effectively applied to the field of nursing. For example, just like IOM, the nursing profession can also form expert consensus committees that play the role of an advisory body. This means that the body can not only make recommendations related to the subject of study but also promote wider discussion, facilitation and cross-disciplinary thinking.

This also means that issues pertaining to health and healthcare can be easily discussed and examined among a panel of experts. The right steps can, as a result, be taken and this will help to ensure that the right decisions are made.

However, rather than conducting simple discussions, the framework also uses consensus committees that are made up of experts in their respective fields. The consensus fields are highly essential to the framework since they play the role of an advisory panel. This means that they convene forums from time to time and even encourage self-evaluation for the purpose of discussing the subject, giving their valuable feedback, and even discussing possible results and remedies. The IOM Framework highlights the importance of being able to know how nurses follow their practices and how efficiently. Moreover, it also allows determine how well nurses are able to determine what type of duties suit them and what do not.

Additionally, nurses will also be able to achieve much higher levels of training and education. This is because they will have a better idea of the type of qualification required for the job. As a result, they will have a much better idea of how to treat patients. Also, there are numerous other benefits that the nurses will gain as a result of the framework. In addition to this, it is also true that nurses act as little less than full partners when they are helping out a healthcare professional or physician. Being full partners will ascertain that the tasks at hand are completed in the most efficient manner.

References